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How does GVC Participation Shape Firms' ESG Compliance?

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Abstract

In today's highly integrated global economy, global value chains (GVCs) are reshaping not only economic activity but also corporate responsibility. This paper examines how firms' participation in GVCs influences their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance, using firm-level data from over 222,000 firms across 159 countries in the World Bank Enterprise Survey. We construct multidimensional ESG indices through a principal component analysis approach and analyze both direct and indirect effects of GVC integration while accounting for firm heterogeneity and potential endogeneity. Our findings show that GVC engagement significantly enhances ESG outcomes, particularly in the environmental and governance dimensions, with larger, older, publicly-owned and manufacturing-sector firms benefiting the most. Female-managed firms, however, face persistent structural barriers. Moreover, firms in developed countries and regions benefit most. Mediation analysis identifies innovation, business strategy, and access to finance as key indirect channels through which GVCs enhance ESG compliance. Robustness checks confirm that deeper integration yields greater sustainability gains, and the results are robust to endogeneity issues.

Keywords: global value chains, environment, social, governance, ESG

JEL classification: F12, F14, F15, F18, F61, F64

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1. Introduction

The link between global value chain (GVC) participation and firms' environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance has emerged as one of today's most dynamic areas of research at the crossroads of international economics and sustainability studies (Taglioni and Winkler, 2016). As globalization continues to reshape production systems, firms are no longer connected only by flows of goods, capital, and technology, but also by shared expectations about environmental responsibility, social inclusion, and good governance. At the same time, ESG compliance has evolved from a voluntary practice to a strategic imperative, affecting firms' access to finance, markets, and reputation (Krueger et al., 2020; Martinez-Ferrero and Lozano, 2021). International investors, trade partners, and consumers are demanding higher standards of transparency, accountability, and sustainability (World Bank, 2020; Global Trade Report, 2024). Understanding how GVC participation influences firms' ESG behavior is therefore essential for assessing whether global economic integration can align with sustainable development objectives.

This paper investigates how firms' participation in GVCs affects their ESG compliance using firm-level data from the World Bank Enterprise Survey (WBES). We construct composite indices for the environmental, social, and governance dimensions using principal component analysis (PCA) and estimate the direct and indirect effects of GVC integration on firms' ESG performance. This topic is timely and critical. Indeed, according to the World Bank (2020), over 50% of global trade now takes place within value chains that cross multiple borders, linking firms of all sizes through networks of production, investment, and knowledge exchange. At the same time, more than 90% of the world's largest companies now publish ESG or sustainability reports (KPMG, 2022), reflecting the growing pressure from regulators, investors, and consumers for responsible business conduct. Yet, many firms, especially in developing and emerging economies struggle to meet rising ESG expectations. Participation in GVCs can be a double-edged sword: a source of sustainability norms, but also of compliance pressure (Makhdalena et al., 2023). Understanding how GVC participation shapes firms' ESG performance is therefore essential for shaping trade, and sustainability policy globally (World Bank, 2020).

The relationship between global economic integration - through trade, GVCs, and foreign direct investment (FDI) - and firms' ESG outcomes has become a central theme in international economics. This link is bidirectional: globalization can shape ESG performance, while ESG standards increasingly influence firms' ability to trade and move up the value chain. Although the concept of ESG is increasingly relevant, existing literature does not comprehensively examine it as a unified concept in relation to economic integration. Early work focused on the environmental consequences of trade and FDI, identifying mechanisms such as the "pollution haven"⁴ effect (Antweiler et al., 2001; Cole & Elliott, 2003; Copeland & Taylor, 2003) and "pollution halo"⁵ effect (Cole et al., 2008; Paziienza, 2019; Zhang and Zhou, 2016). Later studies extended this to

⁴ The "pollution haven" hypothesis posits that as countries liberalize trade and attract foreign investment, they may draw in firms seeking to relocate their most pollution-intensive activities to regions with lax environmental regulations.

⁵ The "pollution halo" hypothesis suggests that trade and foreign investment can lead to improved environmental performance in host countries, as foreign firms often bring cleaner technologies and higher environmental standards.

GVCs, emphasizing that global buyers and lead firms transmit environmental and labor standards to suppliers, encouraging compliance with international norms (Gereffi, 1999; Taglioni & Winkler, 2016; Hua et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021; Bazillier and Rana, 2025). Firm-level evidence supports the idea that GVC integration fosters greener technologies and cleaner production processes, especially when linked to regulatory oversight or buyer requirements (Hu et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2024). Other scholars highlight the social dimension, showing that GVC participation can both generate employment and exacerbate inequalities, depending on local institutions and governance quality (Goldberg & Pavcnik, 2007; Tejani & Milberg, 2016; Carneiro et al., 2023). In parallel, a growing body of work investigates how trade and investment liberalization affect governance systems, finding that GVCs can promote better business practices and transparency through supplier monitoring and international compliance mechanisms (Distelhorst & Locke, 2018; Pietrobelli & Rabellotti, 2011; Taglioni & Winkler, 2016). However, this literature largely treats environmental, social, and governance outcomes separately, and often relies on country- or sector-level data rather than firm-level evidence. Only two studies have analyzed ESG as a unified concept rather than as separate environmental, social, or governance dimensions: Xu and Wu (2022), who examine how import competition from China affects U.S. firms' ESG engagement, and Chen et al. (2025), who explore how trade policy uncertainty shapes ESG performance in Chinese firms. The interplay between GVC participation and an integrated ESG framework remains insufficiently explored, particularly in emerging and developing economies.

This paper advances the literature in four key ways. First, it offers one of the few comprehensive analyses that examines the three ESG pillars - environmental, social, and governance – separately then jointly, using micro-level data across a wide set of sectors as well as developed and developing countries. By constructing firm-level ESG indices, the paper captures multidimensional sustainability outcomes rather than relying on single proxies. Second, it specifically examines how GVC participation, as a key aspect of global economic integration, influences firms' overall ESG adoption, an area that has not been explored before. Third, the paper uses mediation analysis to identify the mechanisms through which GVC participation enhances ESG performance, highlighting the roles of R&D, business strategy, and access to finance as critical transmission channels. Fourth, by exploring how GVC participation interacts with firm characteristics, the study sheds light on how internal attributes can strengthen or modulate the influence of global integration on ESG adoption. This approach emphasizes the dynamic interplay between external GVC pressures and internal firm factors in shaping sustainability practices.

To investigate the determinants of firms' ESG performance, we use firm-level data from the WBES, encompassing over 222,000 firms across 159 countries and 366 surveys since 2006. We estimate regressions with the dependent variable alternating between the environmental, social, and governance indices, as well as a composite ESG index combining all three dimensions. Each index is constructed using PCA, which extracts latent factors from multiple correlated indicators, reducing measurement error and capturing the underlying ESG dimension. Our controls include firm characteristics - such as size, age, manager gender, and public ownership - commonly associated with ESG performance in the literature. The key variable of interest is GVC participation, measured following Dovis and Zaki (2020). Because firms with stronger ESG practices may be more attractive to international buyers or investors - making them more likely to

participate in GVCs - we address potential endogeneity using both instrumental variables (IV) and Propensity Score Matching (PSM).

Our results reveal that GVC participation significantly improves firms' ESG performance, with the strongest effects on the environmental and governance dimensions. Larger and older firms, as well as those in the manufacturing sector or with public ownership, are better positioned to capitalize on GVC-related sustainability spillovers. By contrast, the weaker effects observed for female-managed firms suggest persistent structural barriers to fully benefiting from global integration. The positive relationship between GVC participation and ESG performance is considerably stronger in high-income countries and the European Union, but weaker in regions such as MENA and Eastern Europe. Mediation analysis further confirms that the direct effect of GVC participation on ESG outcomes is dominant, and that innovation, strategic orientation, and financial access are the principal channels through which GVCs indirectly promote ESG compliance. The robustness analysis using a stricter definition of GVCs, which incorporates trade, foreign ownership, and international certification, demonstrates that deeper global integration yields the most substantial sustainability gains. Our results are robust to endogeneity concerns.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the related literature and discusses the theoretical determinants of ESG adoption. Section 3 describes the data, and discusses the stylized facts. Section 4 details the empirical methodology. Section 5 reports and discusses the results, including heterogeneity and mediation analyses. Section 6 concludes with a summary of findings and their policy implications.

2. Literature Review

The relationship between trade, GVCs, and ESG has received growing attention in the economic literature. This section presents two strands of the literature that we rely on in our paper: on the one hand, the key determinants of ESG and, on the other, the impact of trade and GVCs on the three pillars of ESG.

2.1. Determinants of ESG adoption

To adopt ESG practices, firms must respond to a set of determinants that can be described through three theoretical lenses: stakeholder theory, legitimacy theory, and institutional theory. Firstly, Stakeholder theory is an important lens to understand the determinants of ESG. Freeman (1984) defined stakeholders as any individual or group of people who can affect or be affected by the activities of an organization. Stakeholders encompass the environment, employees, investors, suppliers, customers, policymakers, government and non-government organizations. Employees can influence firms' environmental performance through their behaviors such as reducing energy use, minimizing waste, and responsibly managing resources, which, in turn, support sustainability actions. Alt *et al.*, (2015) argue that shared vision unites the organization behind environmental goals, making it possible to implement effective, proactive strategies that drive meaningful progress toward corporate sustainability. In addition, education and awareness enhance ESG adoption by providing communities with the long-term benefits of sustainable practices, and with

the knowledge to incorporate environmental, social and governance factors into their decision-making process (Ong *et al.*, 2025; Lin *et al.*, 2023; Kang and Arikrishnan, 2024). Integrating artificial intelligence and blockchain technology can also strengthen ESG performance through identifying enterprise risks and optimizing sustainability strategies (Nguyen *et al.*, 2025). Customers who are aware of sustainability tend to prioritize ESG considerations in their purchasing decisions. In this context, Simon-Kucher International (2024) indicates that a substantial portion of consumers are willing to pay a premium for sustainable products, with the willingness increasing from 35% to 54% between 2022 and 2024.

Secondly, under legitimacy theory, firms seek to be perceived as legitimate in the eyes of the public. Suchman (1995) defined the legitimacy theory as “*a generalized perception or assumption that the actions of an entity are desirable, proper, or appropriate within some socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs, and definitions*”. From this perspective, the presence of government ownership, measured by the number of shares held by the government, is an important source of firms’ legitimacy. It might encourage firms’ ESG practices, since governments often promote social and environmental protection through regulations, e.g. laws, rules, and government oversight. Wang *et al.*, (2018) find strong evidence that politically embedded firms are more likely to issue corporate social responsibility reports than firms without political embeddedness. Additionally, Zhang *et al.*, (2023) show that, in China, firms with government ownership are more motivated to improve ESG performance because it increases their chance of receiving government subsidies. Parallel to government-ownership, the firm size, commonly measured by firm’s total assets, has been found to positively influence firms’ ESG scores (Abdul Rahaman and Alsayegh, 2021; El Khoury *et al.*, 2021). Larger firms place greater emphasis on ESG reporting than smaller firms because they are more exposed to public opinion and have greater concerns about their reputation. Similarly, Bissoondoyal-Bheenick *et al.*, (2023) show that larger firms tend to invest into ESG activities due the economies of scale and to better reflect stakeholders’ demands. Grassa *et al.*, (2024) find that firm size has a positive and significant effect on ESG rating, indicating that larger firms have greater capacity to implement ESG strategies.

Lastly, focusing on Institutional theory, firms are deeply influenced by the institutional environment, such as social norms, regulatory pressures and governance structures in which they operate (Meyer and Rowan, 1977). From this perspective, institutional ownership is argued to play a critical role in enhancing firms’ ESG performance by providing stronger monitoring incentives and improving corporate governance (Sun and Zhao, 2024). Empirically, Qasem *et al.*, (2022) find that institutional ownership is significantly and positively related to firms’ EGS reporting. Likewise, Wang *et al.*, (2023) show that both long-term pressure insensitive and short-term pressure sensitive institutional investors positively influence firms’ ESG performance. In contrast, Martinez-Ferrero and Lozano (2021) find U-shaped relationship between ESG performance and institutional ownership in emerging countries. Similarly to institutional ownership, ownership concentration plays a moderating role in enhancing firms’ ESG. Jung (2023) finds that ownership concentration significantly moderates the connection between ESG performance and corporate value. Moreover, Yang *et al.*, (2024) demonstrate that ownership concentration has an internal moderating role on the connection between female executives and corporate ESG performance.

Moreover, according to institutional theory, the board gender diversity, measured by the presence or proportion of women on the board, might influence how firms' organizational structure aligns with its ESG performance. In this context, Khemakhem *et al.*, (2022) investigate the relationship between gender diversity on board committees and ESG disclosure among Canadian listed companies and find a positive and significant relationship. These findings align with those of Nuhu and Alam (2023), Wasiuzzaman and Abdul Wahab, (2025) and Zhou and Lok (2024) who also emphasize the positive role of gender-diverse boards in enhancing ESG performance. Table A1 in the appendix provides an overview of recent literature on ESG determinants.

2.2. GVC, Trade and ESG

While the concept of ESG is increasingly relevant, existing literature does not comprehensively examine it as a unified concept in relation to global economic integration, notably trade and GVCs, except for a few studies such as Xu and Wu (2022) and Chen *et al.*, (2025).

Regarding the environmental component, international trade plays a complex and often contradictory role in shaping environmental quality, as suggested by a wide body of literature. In fact, trade expansion can lead to environmental degradation due to the scale effect, which arises when increased economic activity from trade boosts pollution levels (Mutascu, 2018; Shahbaz *et al.*, 2016). Trade can also positively impact environmental quality through the technique effect and composition effect. As trade increases incomes, it may strengthen environmental regulations and promote cleaner production technologies. The composition effect introduces two critical hypotheses: the displacement hypothesis and the pollution-haven hypothesis. The displacement hypothesis suggests that trade liberalization allows pollution-intensive industries to grow more rapidly in developing countries due to lack environmental regulations (Harrison, 1995; Rock, 1996). The pollution haven, closely related, suggests that when countries open up to trade and FDI, they may attract foreign companies that move their most polluting activities to places with weak environmental laws. Additionally, research on GVCs shows that when local firms participate in more advanced parts of the value chain, they often face pressure from international buyers to meet higher environmental standards, especially in industries where large global firms set the rules, such as clothing and electronics (Taglioni & Winkler, 2016). Hu *et al.*, (2021) find that an improvement in a country's position within GVCs significantly enhances the efficiency of green technology innovation. Similarly, Wang *et al.*, (2021) examine the links between GVC participation, technological advancement, and environmental pollution in developing country industries, concluding that once GVC participation reaches a certain threshold, technological progress can play a meaningful role in reducing pollution. In line with these findings, a series of empirical studies confirm that GVC participation has a significant and positive impact on environmental performance (Hua *et al.*, 2020; Hoa *et al.*, 2023; Siewers *et al.*, 2024; Wu *et al.*, 2024).

As per the social dimension, the social effects of trade and GVCs are mixed. On the one hand, some studies highlight the negative social effects of globalization. For instance, Goldberg and Pavcnik (2007) find that trade liberalization was associated with increased wage inequality in developing countries. This was often attributed to skill-biased technological change, whereby trade induces a shift in labor demand towards more skilled workers, as well as the displacement of low-

skilled labor in import-competing sectors. Moreover, Wood (1997) emphasizes how trade exacerbated inequalities by reinforcing structural labor market disparities between skilled and unskilled workers in Latin America. Tejani and Milberg (2016) analyze gendered employment patterns in GVCs and find that while women have gained employment in export-oriented industries, they are often concentrated in low-wage, labor-intensive jobs with limited mobility. On the flip side, other studies emphasize how GVC participation can lead to positive social outcomes. Barrientos *et al.*, (2011) highlight the role of consumer and civil society pressure in improving labor standards in GVC-linked industries like apparel, horticulture, and electronics. These pressures can prompt lead firms to enforce better labor practices through codes of conduct and social audits, especially when reputational risks are high. Lopez-Acevedo *et al.*, (2017) show that exporting firms in developing countries tend to offer better jobs, with higher wages, better training, and more secure employment, to their formal workforce. Taglioni and Winkler (2016) also argue that GVC participation can act as a channel for upgrading workers' skills and transferring knowledge across firms and borders.

Finally, for governance, the relationship between trade, GVC, FDI and institutional or governance outcomes is deeply complex and not conclusive. On the one hand, trade liberalization and FDI are often theorized to promote better governance and institutional development by exposing domestic firms and governments to international norms, standards, and compliance mechanisms. For instance, Dollar and Kraay (2003) argue that globalization is associated with improved governance in low-income countries, while Blonigen and Wang (2005) find that FDI brings stronger corporate governance practices and compliance incentives to the host country. However, the extent to which these benefits materialize highly depends on pre-existing domestic institutional quality. In fact, some studies suggest that the pressures of globalization, especially from lowering tariffs, can lead to a "race to the bottom" in regulations, where governments relax labor and environmental protections to stay competitive and protect jobs or tax income (Drezner, 2001). Several country-level empirical studies show that trade openness can weaken collective labor rights and reduce workers' bargaining power, particularly in developing countries (Mosley and Uno, 2007). By contrast, another group of studies highlights that trade liberalization often goes hand in hand with efforts to align or harmonize regulatory standards. When powerful countries have higher standards, they can push their trade partners to adopt similar rules, leading to upward harmonization as trade expands (Vogel, 1995). Firm-level evidence provides further nuance to these institutional dynamics. Distelhorst and Locke (2018), using a rich dataset of over 2,000 manufacturing establishments across 36 developing countries, challenge the "race to the bottom" hypothesis by showing that multinational buyers, particularly retail importers, reward suppliers for adhering to higher labor and environmental standards. Their study finds that exporters who comply with such standards experience a 4% annual increase in purchasing, driven largely by the apparel sector. This suggests that under the right governance structures and supply chain pressures, trade and GVC participation can serve as conduits for improving institutional quality and social standards. In the same vein, Pietrobelli and Rabellotti (2011) highlight that GVCs often impose standards—such as quality assurance, labor practices, and environmental compliance—on local suppliers, which can indirectly improve institutional practices, especially in areas such as labor inspection and regulatory enforcement. Similarly, Taglioni and Winkler (2016) argue that GVC participation can

foster better governance through three main channels: (1) increased demand for regulatory coherence and contract enforcement to attract and retain foreign investors; (2) knowledge and norm diffusion from lead firms and multinational corporations; and (3) pressure to improve bureaucratic efficiency to reduce trade frictions.

Against this background, our paper tries to bridge the gap between these two strands of the literature to see how GVC affects ESG practices. Moreover, it goes beyond the simple measures of individual components of ESG by calculating a comprehensive measure that considers several dimensions related to the environment, social aspects and governance.

3. Data and Stylized Facts

This section presents the main stylized facts derived from our dataset and illustrates them with three emblematic cases—Schneider Electric, Ørsted, and Unilever—which exemplify how global value chain (GVC) participation and firm characteristics shape ESG performance⁶.

Our sample comprises 222,000 firms surveyed through WBES, since 2006 firms across 159 countries, and includes a diverse range of industries and firm sizes. The data capture detailed information on business characteristics, operational challenges, access to finance, innovation activities, and interactions with the regulatory environment⁷.

We construct 4 ESG indices from the WBES database, covering multiple environmental, social, and governance indicators, using PCA as follows:

The ENV index includes available firm-level indicators related to environmental practices by the firm such as: the adoption of waste minimization, recycling and waste management measures; the adoption of a more climate-friendly energy generation on site; the adoption of energy management measures; the adoption of air pollution control measures; the adoption of water management measures; and the adoption of any measures to enhance energy efficiency. Indeed, as discussed in the literature on the stakeholder-driven determinants of the ESG literature, management and employees can influence firms' environmental performance through their behaviors such as reducing energy use, minimizing waste, and responsibly managing resources.

The GOV index includes available firm-level indicators that are found to affect the firm's governance practices, distinguishing between factors that enhance governance practices and those that undermine them. Variables that improve governance include: whether financial statements were checked and certified by external auditor in last year, reflecting transparency and accountability; the existence of directors or a supervisory board, which indicates a structured oversight mechanism; the presence of female owners or board members, as a growing body of research shows that gender diversity at the top level strengthens governance quality and ESG

⁶ Table B2 in Appendix B provides further examples of multinational companies with strong ESG ratings.

⁷ Please see Tables A1 and A2 in Appendix A for a detailed description of our sample.

performance (Khemakhem et al., 2022; Nuhu and Alam, 2023; Wasiuzzaman and Abdul Wahab, 2025). Conversely, variables that weaken governance include: whether the owner, CEO, top manager, or board member has ever been elected or appointed to a political position, as political connections may create conflicts of interest and reduce managerial accountability; the share of total annual sales paid in informal payments, which serves as a proxy for corruption and weak institutional control.

The SOCIAL index includes available firm-level indicators that are found to affect the firm's social outcomes practices such as: whether the firm adopts formal training of employees, in line with the literature highlighting that education and awareness about the importance and long-term benefits of sustainable practices are a key factor enhancing ESG (Ong *et al.*, 2025; Kang and Arikrishnan, 2024); the share of female employees, used as a proxy of the firm's commitment to diversity, equity, and inclusion; and the frequency of top manager meetings with employees in production/services.

The composite ESG index is computed by combining the three PCA-derived indices to capture overall ESG performance.

Figures 1 and 2 provide strong empirical visualizations, from our sample, that reinforce the arguments and examples presented in the preceding discussion of successful multinational firms with robust ESG practices and deep global value chain (GVC) integration.

Figure 1 displays ESG indicators by firm size, revealing a clear positive relationship between firm scale and ESG performance. Larger firms consistently outperform smaller ones across environmental, social, and governance dimensions. This result confirms the theoretical and empirical evidence discussed earlier in the paper: larger firms tend to have more resources, greater organizational capacity, and stronger reputational incentives to comply with international sustainability standards. The experiences of Schneider Electric, Ørsted, and Unilever vividly illustrate this pattern:

Schneider Electric, a French global leader in energy management and automation, leverages its global scale and R&D investments to deliver digital and clean-energy solutions worldwide. Operating through hubs in the U.S., Europe, and the Middle East/Asia, Schneider integrates sustainability into its core operations. In 2025, it received an A+ ESG grade from Corporate Knights, a top-tier AAA rating from MSCI (2025), and a "Low Risk" Sustainalytics (2025) rating, reflecting its strong ESG performance (Schneider Electric, 2025).

In a similar way, Ørsted, Danish multinational company and a global leader in renewable energy solutions, transitioned from a fossil-fuel-based utility to the world's largest offshore wind developer. With over 8,300 employees and €9.5 billion in revenue, the company demonstrates how large-scale firms mobilize resources and innovation networks to achieve decarbonization. Ørsted was awarded a Platinum Medal by EcoVadis, ranked among the top 10 most sustainable energy companies by Corporate Knights, and received AAA rating from MSCI (2025) and Low Risk rating from Sustainalytics (2025) (Ørsted, 2025).

Finally, Unilever, a British multinational company standing as one of the world's largest fast-moving consumer goods companies, institutionalizes ESG norms across its vast global operations, employing over 128,000 people and partnering with 57,000 suppliers. Its Board Diversity Policy promotes gender, ethnic, and experiential diversity in governance. In 2025, Unilever ranked 76th globally in Corporate Knights, achieved a AAA ESG rating from MSCI (2025), and a Low Risk Sustainalytics (2025) rating, highlighting how large firms systematically embed ESG practices (Unilever, 2025).

Figure 2 compares ESG indicators across GVC-participating and non-participating firms, showing that firms integrated into GVCs exhibit higher ESG scores. Firms that import, export, or engage with foreign partners are exposed to buyer pressure, supplier audits, and global compliance frameworks, which collectively foster better environmental, social, and governance outcomes. Indeed, GVC-participating firms often operate under international environmental standards imposed by global buyers or partners. For instance, suppliers and manufacturers in a multinational's network may be audited for compliance with renewable energy use, carbon footprint limits, or water conservation practices. This exposure drives firms to implement systematic environmental policies and adopt innovative technologies to meet global sustainability benchmarks. Moreover, GVC-participating firms in global value chains are subject to scrutiny regarding labor conditions, human rights, and community engagement. Buyers often require adherence to social standards, including fair labor practices, safe working conditions, and equitable treatment of employees. Last but not least, GVC-participating firms are usually demanded by global partners to comply with rigorous reporting, anti-corruption measures, and board accountability. This motivates firms to strengthen governance structures, adopt risk management practices, and formalize policies for compliance and stakeholder engagement.

The earlier examples of multinational companies illustrate this dynamic:

- Schneider Electric works with partners across continents to promote resource efficiency and renewable energy solutions, embedding ESG principles throughout its supply chain. Environmentally, it promotes renewable energy adoption and energy-efficient technologies among partners. Socially, it ensures labor standards, health, and safety measures are upheld across its suppliers. In governance, Schneider applies rigorous reporting frameworks and audits to maintain compliance and transparency across global projects (Schneider Electric, 2025).
- Ørsted coordinates with international suppliers and technology partners to comply with rigorous sustainability standards, demonstrating how GVC integration reinforces environmental leadership. Its collaboration with global firms like Ericsson, IKEA, and Microsoft strengthens ESG outcomes across its operations. Environmentally, it drives decarbonization through large-scale renewable energy projects. Socially, it engages with local communities and ensures safe working conditions in all its operations and partner sites. Governance-wise, Ørsted adheres to strict anti-corruption policies, ESG risk management, and reporting standards, ensuring accountability across its global value chain (Ørsted, 2025).
- Unilever disseminates sustainability norms across its 57,000 suppliers, promoting responsible sourcing, waste reduction, and labor inclusion. Its GVC engagement allows the

company to enforce ESG principles throughout its global supply chain. Environmental practices include responsible sourcing and waste reduction initiatives. Socially, it promotes diversity, equity, inclusion, and fair labor practices across its operations and supplier networks. Governance is strengthened through transparent reporting, board diversity, and supplier compliance programs, ensuring ESG principles are institutionalized globally (Unilever, 2025).

Figure 1: ESG indicators by firm size

Source: Authors’ own elaboration.

Figure 2: ESG indicators and GVC participation

Source: Authors’ own elaboration.

Additionally, Figure A1 in Appendix A shows that the overall ESG score, as well as the governance and environmental indices, tend to be higher for firms managed by men, whereas the

social index is slightly higher for firms managed by women. Indeed, female-led firms often prioritize employee well-being, community engagement, and social initiatives (McKinsey & Company, 2022). Figure A2 in Appendix A highlights a notable difference between publicly-owned and privately-owned firms, with public firms exhibiting relatively higher scores across all ESG indicators, in line with the literature (Wang et al, 2018; Zhang et al., 2023).

Taken together, these patterns suggest that successful ESG integration is influenced by both internal firm characteristics, such as size, management and ownership structure, as well as external factors, such as participation in GVCs, underscoring the interplay between internal and external drivers of sustainability.

4. Empirical Specification

To examine the determinants of firms' ESG performance, we estimate regressions where the dependent variable alternates between the environmental index (ENV), social index (SOCIAL), governance index (GOV), and a composite ESG index combining all three dimensions. Each index is constructed using principal component analysis (PCA), which extracts latent factors from multiple correlated indicators, reducing measurement error and capturing the underlying ESG dimension. This approach allows us to capture heterogeneity across ESG pillars while also analyzing overall corporate sustainability.

The baseline specification for our pooled data is as follows:

$$DEP_{isjt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GVC_{isjt} + \gamma' X_{isjt} + \mu_j + \lambda_s + \tau_t + \epsilon_{isjt}$$

Where:

DEP_{isjt} is the dependent variable representing alternatively ENV_{isjt} , GOV_{isjt} , $SOCIAL_{isjt}$ and ESG_{isjt} compliance for firm i in sector s in country j at time t .

The independent variables include GVC_{isjt} as a measure of firm i 's participation in GVCs in sector s in country j at time t . DAVIS and ZAKI (2020) used microdata from WBES to construct composite indicators used as proxies for GVCs participation at the firm level. We rely on the least strict definition for GVC integration, capturing whether the firm exports and imports simultaneously in the designed sector. X_{isjt} is a vector of control variables for firm i in sector s in country j at time t , chosen based on the literature. This includes: *Firm size* that is measured with a categorical variable taking four values: Micro (Less than 5, reference category), Small (5 – 19 employees), Medium (20 – 99 employees) and Large (100 + employees). Firm size reflects legitimacy- and resource-driven determinants, with larger firms typically demonstrating higher ESG performance due to greater public scrutiny, media exposure, and resource availability (Wong *et al.*, 2020; Abdul Rahaman and Alsayegh, 2021; Grassa *et al.*, 2023; Nguyen *et al.*, 2025). We also include the firm age $Ln(Age)$ as older firms may have more established governance structures and legitimacy, influencing ESG adoption (Ogboro *et al.*, 2024; Qasim *et al.*, 2022). Third, we control for the gender of the manager with a dummy variable taking the value of 1 if the firm is managed by a

female, and 0 otherwise. This is aligned with institutional theory evidence that gender-diverse leadership enhances ESG disclosure and social responsibility outcomes (Nuhu and Alam, 2023; Wasiuzzaman and Abdul Wahab, 2025). Finally, we control for public ownership captured by the percentage of government ownership. As per the legitimacy theory, firms with public or state involvement are more prone to adopt and report ESG practices, as governments often promote social and environmental protection through regulations (Wang *et al.*, 2018; Zhang *et al.*, 2023). We also add country (μ_j), sector (λ_s) and year (t_t) fixed effects to capture unobserved heterogeneity at the country, sector and year level. $\epsilon_{i,s,c,t}$ is the idiosyncratic error term.

Beyond the baseline regressions, we extend the analysis along four dimensions to better understand the channels and heterogeneity underlying the ESG-GVC nexus. First, we examine how GVC participation interacts with firm-specific characteristics, such as age, public ownership, sector of activity, and managerial gender, to assess whether certain traits condition the ability of firms to translate global linkages into ESG improvements.

Second, we differentiate our sample by level of income (high income vs. low income countries) and region (Latin America (LAC), European Union (EU), Eastern Europe (EE) and Middle East and North Africa (MENA)). Differentiating by income and region captures how varying economic development, governance, and market conditions shape firms' ESG adoption within GVCs. Indeed, firms operating in high-income countries or regions with strong institutions often face stricter regulatory requirements, higher stakeholder expectations, and more developed ESG frameworks, which can amplify the positive impact of GVC participation on ESG adoption. Conversely, firms in low-income countries or regions with weaker governance may encounter resource constraints or limited enforcement of ESG standards, making GVC integration a crucial channel for accessing knowledge, technology, and international pressures that promote ESG compliance.

Third, we employ mediation analysis to disentangle the direct and indirect pathways through which GVC integration shapes ESG performance. Specifically, we consider mediators that the literature identifies as central to ESG outcomes such as R&D intensity, business strategy, workforce composition, access to finance, and formal registration, thereby clarifying the mechanisms at play. Indeed, as previously discussed, innovation and strategic upgrading are key drivers of sustainability adoption, as firms exposed to GVC pressures often respond by investing in R&D and aligning their business strategies with international standards (Nguyen *et al.*, 2025; Taglioni & Winkler, 2016). Access to finance is also highlighted in the literature as a critical enabler of ESG practices, since compliance with environmental and social standards typically requires upfront investments in cleaner technologies, reporting systems, and workforce training (Grassa *et al.*, 2023). Similarly, workforce skills and composition are emphasized in studies linking education, awareness, and employee engagement to the effective implementation of ESG practices (Ong *et al.*, 2025). Finally, formal registration captures the institutional and legitimacy-driven determinants, as compliance with registration and reporting requirements reflects broader firm-level integration into formal governance structures, which is consistently associated with stronger ESG disclosure and adoption (Abdul Rahaman and Alsayegh, 2021).

Finally, to assess the consistency and robustness of our findings, we proceed in two ways. First, we use an alternative definition of GVC participation: the strictest GVC4 measure proposed by

Dovis and Zaki (2020), which jointly captures trade flows, foreign ownership, and international certification. Second, since firms with stronger ESG practices may be more attractive to international buyers or investors - making them more likely to join GVCs - we also address potential endogeneity using IV and PSM. For the IV approach, we use a shift-share type instrument, namely the share of firms that are exporters and importers in sector s in country j at time t , excluding the firm in question. The shift-share type instrument isolates variation in a firm's likelihood of GVC participation that arises from broader industry and country-level global integration shocks, which are plausibly exogenous to the firm's ESG decisions. This makes it a strong and credible instrument for addressing potential endogeneity where the placement is based on unobservables. The PSM method complements this by creating a matched sample of GVC-participating and non-participating firms with similar observable characteristics, such as size, age, ownership structure and management. By comparing firms that are otherwise similar except for their GVC participation status, PSM helps isolate the causal effect of GVC integration on ESG performance.

5. Empirical Results

This section reflects on the empirical analysis by situating the findings within the existing body of literature on GVC participation and ESG performance.

5.1. Baseline Results

Baseline results, summarized in Table 1, show positive and statistically significant effects of GVC participation on ESG outcomes, with the strongest effect observed for the environmental dimension. This finding resonates with studies documenting how international buyers pressure suppliers to adopt greener practices (Gereffi, 1999; Taglioni & Winkler, 2016; Hua et al., 2020; Hu et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2021; Hoa et al., 2023; Siewers and al.; 2024; Wu et al., 2024). Governance improvements are also substantial, reflecting the role of GVC participation in enhancing institutional quality and better governance (Pietrobelli and Rabellotti, 2011; Taglioni and Winkler, 2016; Distelhorst and Locke; 2018). The social outcomes of GVC participation are also positive (Tejani & Milberg, 2016; Zuohang, 2020), although exhibiting a weaker coefficient, echoing the findings in the literature that the social effects of GVC are more ambiguous and highly context-dependent.

Control variables behave consistently with the literature. Larger firms exhibit significantly higher ESG scores across all dimensions, in line with Grassa et al. (2023) and others, who stress size-related resource advantages and reputational pressures. Large firms exhibit the largest coefficient, followed by medium firms, then small firms. Firm size appears to have a stronger effect on governance than on environmental or social outcomes, as larger firms generally have more complex organizational structures, external audits, and formal compliance mechanisms, making governance improvements more size-dependent. However, small firms seem to perform relatively better on the social dimension. Indeed, social practices, such as closer interaction between managers and employees or fostering inclusion, can be better achieved in a small-scale organizational structure. By contrast, environmental measures often require technical investment, and governance practices rely on formal compliance systems, both of which are harder for small firms to implement.

Older firms also perform better on ESG outcomes, consistent with the idea that organizational maturity supports stronger governance structures and legitimacy, influencing ESG adoption (Ogboro et al., 2024). The effect of the firm's age is strongest for the environmental dimension, followed by governance and then social outcomes. The stronger effect of age on the environmental dimension likely reflects the cumulative nature of environmental practices: older firms have had more time to invest in energy efficiency and pollution control. Governance also improves with maturity, as firms establish formal structures and compliance mechanisms over time. Age has the weakest effect on social outcomes because longevity does not guarantee stronger engagement with training, diversity, or inclusion initiatives. Such outcomes are shaped more by current organizational culture, prevailing social norms, and management decisions than by years of experience.

Government ownership positively affects ESG scores, confirming legitimacy-driven determinants (Wang et al., 2018). However, its impact varies across ESG dimensions. Governance outcomes benefit the most because state ownership imposes stricter oversight, accountability, and transparency mechanisms. Environmental performance also improves, though to a lesser extent, as government priorities and regulations can encourage sustainability initiatives, although sometimes constrained by bureaucracy or competing economic objectives. In contrast, social outcomes seem to be negatively affected, as state-owned firms often emphasize political or economic goals over employee welfare, community engagement, or inclusive practices, resulting in weaker social performance relative to private firms.

Interestingly, female managers have a positive but insignificant effect on overall ESG outcomes. Their presence appears to only improve social outcomes, indicating that female managers may primarily influence inclusion, employee relations, and workplace dynamics (McKinsey & Company, 2022). However, female managers show a significant negative effect on governance and environmental outcomes, which could reflect structural or organizational constraints such as limited decision-making authority, or the possibility that women are more often appointed to roles focused on people management rather than environmental or governance responsibilities, limiting their impact on these dimensions.

Table 1: Baseline Results

	Gov.	Env.	Social	ESG
GVC	0.117*** (0.00733)	0.250*** (0.0129)	0.0402*** (0.00447)	0.173*** (0.00766)
Public	0.388*** (0.0260)	0.317*** (0.0455)	-0.0698*** (0.0158)	0.232*** (0.0270)
Fem. Manager	-0.0147* (0.00771)	-0.0376*** (0.0136)	0.0242*** (0.00470)	0.00305 (0.00805)
Ln(Age)	0.0287*** (0.00325)	0.0377*** (0.00573)	0.00535*** (0.00198)	0.0312*** (0.00340)
Small	0.155*** (0.0206)	0.131*** (0.0362)	0.0534*** (0.0125)	0.170*** (0.0215)
Medium	0.373*** (0.0207)	0.310*** (0.0366)	0.206*** (0.0126)	0.482*** (0.0217)
Large	0.623*** (0.0213)	0.609*** (0.0376)	0.517*** (0.0130)	0.997*** (0.0223)
Observations	27,202	26,877	27,201	26,873
R-squared	0.341	0.191	0.345	0.403

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

All regressions include an intercept, country, year and sector fixed effects.

5.2. Extensions

This sub-section examines how GVC participation interacts with specific firm characteristics as well the level of development of the country/region to shape ESG outcomes. The rationale is that firm-level traits, such as age, public ownership, sector of activity, or managerial gender, may condition how effectively a firm leverages GVC engagement to enhance ESG performance. Tables 2 and 3 present the results for the overall ESG index, showing the impact of interacting the GVC variable with each of these characteristics (referred to as “Dimension”).

Notably, Table 2 shows that the positive effect of GVCs on ESG is amplified for older firms, those with public ownership, and firms operating in the manufacturing sector, while the effect weakens for firms led by female managers. The stronger effect in older firms likely reflects their accumulated experience, established routines, and more developed organizational capabilities, which allow them to better respond to the external pressures associated with GVC participation (Ogboro et al., 2024). Similarly, public ownership amplifies the effect because state-owned firms face greater scrutiny, legitimacy pressures, and regulatory oversight, motivating them to adopt more rigorous ESG practices (Wang et al., 2018). In manufacturing firms, the amplification is driven by the sector’s higher exposure to global standards, regulatory compliance, and international buyer requirements, which create stronger incentives to enhance environmental, social, and governance performance. In contrast, the weaker results for female-led firms may

reflect structural barriers, such as limited access to networks, resources, or certification channels, rather than managerial preferences per se.

Moreover, Table 3 shows that the positive effect of GVCs on ESG is amplified for larger firms, likely because they possess greater resources, organizational capacity, and institutional knowledge to comply with international standards and meet the demands of global value chain partners. Larger firms also have more formalized reporting systems, dedicated sustainability teams, and access to networks that facilitate the adoption of ESG practices (Wong et al., 2020)

Table 2: Empirical Results - Interactions I

	Age	Fem. Manager	Public	Manuf.
	ESG	ESG	ESG	ESG
GVC	-0.0236 (0.0255)	0.186*** (0.00813)	0.172*** (0.00771)	0.119*** (0.0132)
Dimension	0.0193*** (0.00370)	0.0207** (0.00893)	0.204*** (0.0315)	
GVC*Dimension	0.0675*** (0.00836)	-0.0892*** (0.0196)	0.0962* (0.0565)	0.0787*** (0.0157)
Observations	26,873	26,873	26,873	26,873
R-squared	0.404	0.403	0.403	0.403

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

All regressions include the controls, an intercept, country, year and sector fixed effects.

Dimension refers to the variable interacted with GVC and included in the first row

Table 3: Empirical Results - Interactions II

Size		Region		Income	
	ESG		ESG		ESG
GVC	0.0766 (0.0728)	GVC	0.184*** (0.0182)	GVC	0.150*** (0.00943)
Small	0.169*** (0.0225)	GVC*EU	0.0421** (0.0210)	GVC*High income	0.0611*** (0.0147)
Medium	0.472*** (0.0228)	GVC*Eastern Europe	-0.0851*** (0.0236)		
Large	0.965*** (0.0238)	GVC*MENA	-0.0575** (0.0249)		
Small*GVC	0.0336 (0.0739)				
Medium*GVC	0.105 (0.0736)				
Large*GVC	0.150** (0.0740)				
Observations	26,873	Observations	26,873	Observations	26,873
R-squared	0.404	R-squared	0.404	R-squared	0.403

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

All regressions include the controls, an intercept, country, year and sector fixed effects.

In the first regression, the reference category is micro firm, the second one Asia, and the third one low and middle-income countries.

We now turn to examine how the interaction terms between GVC participation and firm characteristics affect each of the three ESG dimensions - environmental, social, and governance - to better understand which aspects of sustainability are most influenced by these factors⁸.

The positive sign of the GVC–age interaction is strongest for the environmental dimension, followed by governance, and then social outcomes. As previously mentioned, older firms often have more established operational processes and resources to implement environmental management systems, adopt green technologies, and comply with international environmental standards. Governance benefits next, as older firms tend to have more formalized structures and reporting mechanisms, making it easier to align with compliance and accountability expectations. Social outcomes show the weakest effect because they rely heavily on managerial practices, workplace culture, and employee engagement, which may not automatically improve with firm age (Ogboro *et al.*, 2024; Qasim *et al.*, 2022).

The negative sign of the GVC–female manager interaction is strongest for governance, followed by environmental outcomes, and weakest for social outcomes, suggesting that the positive effect of GVC on each ESG dimension, decreases when the firm is managed by a female. This pattern

⁸ For the sake of brevity, the results are displayed in Tables A3 and A4 in Appendix A.

likely reflects the organizational roles and structural constraints faced by female managers. As well, the lack of resources and strategic investment that can positively impact the environment.

The positive sign of the GVC–manufacturing interaction is strongest for environmental outcomes, followed by governance, and shows no significant effect on social outcomes, suggesting that firms belonging to the manufacturing sector witness an amplified effect of GVC on environmental and governance outcomes. Indeed, manufacturing firms are typically more exposed to international environmental standards, and regulatory requirements, which incentivize investments in energy efficiency, pollution control, and green technologies, explaining the strong environmental impact (Pazienza, 2019). Governance benefits next, as participation in GVCs encourages formalized reporting, compliance mechanisms, and structured oversight in production processes. In contrast, social outcomes are less affected because labor practices, inclusion, and community engagement in manufacturing are often determined by internal human resource policies rather than external GVC pressures, resulting in an insignificant effect (Distelhorst and Locke, 2018).

The positive sign of the GVC-public ownership interaction is strongest for environmental outcomes, followed by social outcomes, while the coefficient for the interaction term is negative for governance. Therefore, state ownership appears to increase the positive effect of GVC on environmental and social outcomes, and decreases it for governance outcomes. Indeed, firms with state-ownership often face high public scrutiny and regulatory expectations, which motivates investments in environmental initiatives such as emission reductions, resource efficiency, and compliance with sustainability standards, explaining the strong environmental effect. Moreover, public ownership can foster community engagement and employee welfare programs aligned with social responsibility mandates, therefore amplifying the effect of GVC on social outcomes (Zhang *et al.*, 2023). However, governance may be negatively affected because state-owned firms can suffer from bureaucratic inefficiencies, political interference, or complex reporting structures that dilute accountability and decision-making effectiveness, limiting the positive impact of GVC participation on governance practices.

The positive sign of the GVC-large firm interaction is strongest for environmental outcomes, while it is not significant for social or governance dimensions, highlighting that large firms only amplify the effect of GVC participation on environmental outcomes only. Large firms typically have greater financial and technical resources, allowing them to invest in environmental management systems, green technologies, and compliance with international environmental standards demanded by GVC partners (Wong *et al.*, 2020; Abdul Rahaman and Alsayegh, 2021). In contrast, social and governance outcomes rely more on organizational culture, managerial practices, and decision-making structures, which may not automatically improve with firm size.

Overall, the analysis shows that GVC participation most strongly enhances environmental performance across firm characteristics, while effects on governance and social dimensions are more variable and context-dependent. This highlights that both external pressures from GVCs and internal firm attributes jointly shape how sustainability practices are adopted.

Table 3 offers additional insights into how regional and income-level characteristics shape the ESG benefits of GVC participation. The table reveals that the positive relationship between GVC participation and ESG performance is significantly stronger for firms located in high-income countries and in the European Union, whereas the effects are weaker for firms in the MENA and Eastern European regions. These findings emphasize that the extent to which GVC participation translate into sustainable outcomes depends heavily on domestic institutional capacity, regulatory enforcement, and the quality of governance structures. In high-income and EU contexts, where regulatory systems and ESG reporting frameworks are well established, firms are better positioned to leverage their GVC linkages to enhance sustainability (Liu, 2022; Agostino, 2023). Conversely, in regions such as MENA and Eastern Europe, weaker institutional frameworks, limited enforcement of environmental standards, and lower public scrutiny reduce the potential for GVC integration to yield similar benefits.

We next examine the effects of GVC participation on governance, social, and environmental outcomes separately across regions and levels of development⁹. The results indicate that GVC participation in the EU significantly improves social outcomes, while the effect on governance is insignificant. In contrast, the effect of GVC on governance and environmental outcomes worsens for firms located in the MENA, while the effect on social outcomes increases. These findings mirror the earlier discussion on the heterogeneity of GVC effects.

This analysis suggests that while GVC integration generates external pressures for sustainability, firm-level internal factors as well the level of development of the country and region determine the extent to which these pressures translate into improved ESG outcomes.

5.3. Which Channels Matter?

Mediation analysis provides a framework to disentangle the mechanisms through which GVC participation influences ESG outcomes, distinguishing between direct and indirect effects. The mediators considered, namely, the firm's characteristics related to R&D expenses, the business strategy, the share of skilled production workers, share of non-production workers, access to finance, and formal registration. are motivated directly by the literature on ESG determinants, as previously argued.

Table 4 highlights how these channels shape ESG performance. The net indirect effect (NIE) captures the portion of the GVC impact transmitted through a mediator, the net direct effect (NDE) represents the effect of GVCs not channeled through the mediator, and the total effect (TE) combines both direct and indirect contributions.

The results show that the direct effect of GVC participation on ESG performance is dominant, positive, and highly significant, indicating that being integrated into global value chains directly exposes firms to international standards, buyer pressure, and global compliance frameworks, which immediately enhance environmental, social, and governance outcomes. The net indirect

⁹ For the sake of brevity, the results are displayed in Table A5 in Appendix A.

effect, while smaller in magnitude, is statistically significant for certain mediators, illustrating the specific mechanisms through which GVC integration further supports ESG adoption.

Among the mediators, R&D intensity and business strategy emerge as particularly important channels. NIE values of 0.0567 for R&D and 0.0773 for business strategy suggest that part of the positive GVC effect on ESG performance operates through firms' innovation efforts and strategic upgrading. In other words, GVC participation encourages firms to invest in research, adopt new technologies, and align their strategic priorities with sustainability goals, which in turn improves ESG outcomes. Access to finance also plays a meaningful role, with an NIE of 0.0206, indicating that financial resources facilitate the implementation of ESG practices by enabling investments in cleaner technologies, staff training, and compliance systems.

By contrast, workforce composition, measured as the share of skilled production and non-production workers, and formal registration do not appear to play significant mediating roles, indicating that GVC-driven ESG improvements are less about immediate labor restructuring and more about innovation, resource allocation, and strategic investment.

Overall, the total effects (TE) remain substantial across all mediators, underscoring that while some pathways contribute more than others, GVC participation consistently enhances ESG performance through both direct and indirect mechanisms.

Table 4: Mediation Analysis

	ESG		
	NIE	NDE	TE
RD	0.0567*** (0.00339)	0.136*** (0.00831)	0.193*** (0.00829)
Bus. Strategy	0.0773*** (0.00384)	0.128*** (0.00793)	0.206*** (0.00832)
Share skilled prod.	-5.93e-05 (0.000146)	0.198*** (0.0105)	0.198*** (0.0105)
Share non prod.	-0.00129* (0.000749)	0.197*** (0.0105)	0.195*** (0.0105)
Formal regis.	-6.22e-05 (0.000802)	0.174*** (0.00835)	0.174*** (0.00831)
Finance	0.0206*** (0.00264)	0.162*** (0.00845)	0.182*** (0.00833)

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

All regressions include the controls, an intercept, country, year and sector fixed effects.

Each row represents a regression with the mediation channel in question.

NIE refers to net indirect effect, NDE refers to net direct effect and TE refers to total effect.

The mediation analysis is further repeated for each of the three ESG dimensions -environmental, social, and governance - and broadly the same patterns apply for each dimension¹⁰. In all cases, the direct effect of GVC participation remains dominant, positive, and highly significant indicating that integration into global value chains consistently drives better ESG performance irrespective of the specific dimension.

The net indirect effects through the mediators, while smaller in magnitude, show that certain channels play a meaningful role in transmitting the benefits of GVC participation. Specifically, R&D intensity, business strategy, and access to finance emerge as the most influential mediators. These channels are particularly relevant for the environmental dimension, suggesting that firms leverage innovation, strategic upgrading, and financial resources to implement cleaner technologies, improve energy efficiency, reduce emissions, and meet international environmental standards.

By contrast, for the social and governance dimensions, the indirect effects are smaller, implying that GVC participation impacts these areas primarily through direct exposure to global standards, stakeholder expectations, and compliance pressures rather than through innovation or strategic investments. In other words, while access to knowledge, technology, and finance facilitates environmental improvements, social outcomes and governance improvements are more directly shaped by international regulations, buyer requirements, and institutional pressures inherent in GVC participation.

5.4. Robustness Checks

To probe the consistency of the estimated effects, we conduct several robustness checks. We first opt for the strictest definition of GVC participation (GVC4) taken from DAVIS and ZAKI (2020), capturing imports and exports, the share of the firm's capital that is owned by a foreign firm, as well as whether the firm has an international certification. Table 5 confirms the stability of results with the alternative definition of GVC participation, strengthening confidence in the findings. Importantly, the stronger coefficients for the stricter GVC4 definition, relative to the baseline regression, suggests that deeper integration, combining trade, foreign ownership, and certification, produces the most pronounced ESG improvements, echoing the literature on deep trade agreements and enforceable provisions (Laget et al., 2018; Osanago, 2020; Fontagné et al., 2023; Guillin et al., 2023).

¹⁰ For the sake of brevity, the results are displayed in Tables A6 in Appendix A.

Table 5: Alternative definition of GVC

	Gov.	Env.	Social	ESG
GVC	0.217*** (0.0179)	0.394*** (0.0317)	0.0817*** (0.0109)	0.309*** (0.0188)
Public	0.381*** (0.0260)	0.302*** (0.0457)	-0.0723*** (0.0158)	0.221*** (0.0271)
Fem. Manager	-0.0169** (0.00773)	-0.0423*** (0.0136)	0.0235*** (0.00470)	-0.000153 (0.00808)
Ln(Age)	0.0300*** (0.00326)	0.0402*** (0.00575)	0.00579*** (0.00198)	0.0330*** (0.00341)
Small	0.157*** (0.0206)	0.136*** (0.0364)	0.0543*** (0.0125)	0.173*** (0.0216)
Medium	0.386*** (0.0208)	0.338*** (0.0367)	0.210*** (0.0126)	0.501*** (0.0218)
Large	0.639*** (0.0213)	0.650*** (0.0377)	0.522*** (0.0130)	1.021*** (0.0223)
Observations	27,202	26,877	27,201	26,873
R-squared	0.338	0.184	0.345	0.397

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

All regressions include an intercept, country, year and sector fixed effects.

Finally, Table 6 presents a summary of robustness tests using IV and PSM, to address potential endogeneity in the main regressions. The results confirm that GVC participation continues to exert a positive and statistically significant effect on ESG performance across both methods. Table A7 in Appendix A presents the first-stage regression of the IV approach, where GVC participation is instrumented by the shift-share type variable (“GVC inst.”). The instrument is strongly significant and positive, confirming its relevance. The Durbin and Wu-Hausman tests have p-values above 0.05 indicating no significant autocorrelation in the model's residuals. Moreover, the F-stat of the first stage is high confirming that our instrument is not weak.

Concerning the placement on observables, the PSM approach, in particular, is crucial for validating the causal relationship between GVC integration and ESG outcomes. By matching GVC-participating firms with non-participating firms that share similar observable characteristics, such as size, age, ownership structure and management, PSM isolates the effect of GVC participation itself from other confounding factors. Table A8 in Appendix B reports the balancing test after matching treated (GVC-participating) and control (non-participating) firms using PMS. The t-tests assess whether observable firm characteristics differ significantly between groups after matching. Most variables show no significant differences (at the 10% significance level), indicating good balance, namely that the matching procedure effectively created comparable groups. Therefore, the PSM results generally confirm that treatment and control groups are well balanced on observable covariates, supporting the validity of subsequent causal inference on ESG outcomes. Figure A3 in Appendix A illustrates the distribution of propensity scores for treated and control firms. The overlap between both distributions shows substantial common support, meaning that

most treated firms have comparable control counterparts. This visual evidence reinforces the balancing results in Table A7, indicating that the matching sample is well constructed and suitable for estimating the average treatment effect of GVC participation on ESG adoption.

Table 6: Alternative estimation methods

	IV	PSM
	ESG	ESG
GVC	0.0898*	0.187***
	(0.0488)	(0.0162)
Observations	26,873	26,873

Standard errors in parentheses

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

All regressions include an intercept, country, year and sector fixed effects.

Taken together, the results are summarized in the following points. First, GVC participation is a key driver of ESG adoption, especially for environmental and governance practices. Second, firm size, age, the manufacturing sector and government ownership amplify the effect of GVC participation on ESG outcomes, while leadership diversity attenuates it. Third, the positive link between GVC participation and ESG performance is notably stronger for firms in high-income countries and the European Union, while it is weaker in the MENA and Eastern European regions. Fourth, to complement the strong direct effect of GVC on ESG adoption, innovation, business strategy, and financing appear as central indirect channels linking GVC participation to ESG. Finally, deeper forms of GVC integration, involving certification and foreign ownership, yield the largest ESG gains.

6. Conclusion and Policy Implications

This paper investigates the impact of firms' participation in GVCs on their ESG performance. By developing multidimensional ESG indices and connecting them to firm-level indicators of GVC integration, it offers new evidence on how globalization influences corporate sustainability practices. This issue is particularly relevant as global trade becomes increasingly linked to sustainability goals, and as ESG compliance emerges as both a source of competitive advantage and a requirement for accessing international markets.

The analysis relied on firm-level data from the WBES and used principal component analysis to build composite indices for environmental, social, and governance dimensions as well as a combined index for the three dimensions. The baseline results, supported by robustness checks, indicate that GVC participation significantly enhances ESG outcomes, with particularly strong effects on environmental and governance performance. Interaction analyses show that firm characteristics condition these effects: size, age, public ownership, and sectoral context amplify the ESG benefits of GVC integration, while female managerial leadership appears to attenuate them, likely due to structural barriers. The strength of the positive relationship between GVC participation and ESG performance depends on a country's level of development: it is considerably

stronger in high-income countries and the European Union, but weaker in less-developed regions such as MENA and Eastern Europe. The mediation analysis further shows that GVC participation has a strong direct impact on ESG compliance, while innovation, business strategy, and access to finance serve as the main indirect pathways through which GVCs enhance ESG performance. Our results are robust to endogeneity.

The findings carry several policy implications. First, promoting GVC participation can be a lever for advancing sustainability, provided that firms have the institutional and financial capacity to comply with ESG standards. Policymakers should therefore pair trade and investment policies with supportive frameworks for ESG reporting, innovation and financing. Second, the results underline the importance of strengthening public–private partnerships to encourage responsible practices in GVC-linked sectors, especially manufacturing, where environmental externalities are high but opportunities for green upgrading are also substantial. Third, gender-sensitive policies are needed to address the constraints faced by female managers and entrepreneurs, enabling them to fully benefit from internationalization and sustainability transitions. Finally, since deeper GVC integration through certification and foreign partnerships produces the largest ESG improvements, policymakers should facilitate firms’ access to international standards and accreditation systems that enhance both competitiveness and sustainability.

Overall, this study highlights that GVC participation is not only an economic integration mechanism but also a potential catalyst for responsible business conduct. By leveraging trade linkages, innovation, and institutional frameworks, countries can align globalization with sustainable development objectives.

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Appendix A

Table A1. Sample composition – Number of firms per country

Albania	377	Lithuania	358
Armenia	546	Malta	242
Azerbaijan	225	Moldova	360
Belarus	600	Mongolia	360
Bosnia and Herz.	362	Montenegro	150
Bulgaria	772	Morocco	661
Croatia	404	North Macedonia	360
Cyprus	360	Poland	1,369
Czech Rep.	502	Portugal	1,062
Egypt	3,075	Romania	814
Estonia	360	Russia	1,323
Georgia	581	Serbia	361
Greece	600	Slovak Rep.	429
Hungary	805	Slovenia	409
Italy	760	Tajikistan	352
Jordan	601	Tunisia	615
Kazakhstan	1,446	Turkey	1,663
Kosovo	271	Ukraine	1,337
Kyrgyz Rep.	360	Uzbekistan	1,239
Latvia	359	West Bank and Gaza	365
Lebanon	532		

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Table A2. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
Governance	27,723	0.00	0.55	-0.54	0.86
Environment	27,383	0.00	0.86	-0.70	2.36
Social	27,722	0.00	0.33	-0.34	0.91
ESG	27,379	0.00	0.60	-0.82	2.02
GVC	27,727	0.22	0.41	0.00	1.00
Fem. Manager	27,726	0.16	0.36	0.00	1.00
Public	27,727	0.01	0.11	0.00	1.00
Ln(age)	27,707	2.80	0.90	0.00	7.62
Size	27,228	2.70	0.79	1.00	4.00

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Table A3: Interactions by ESG Dimension I

	Age		
	Gov.	Env.	Social
GVC	-0.0581** (0.0245)	-0.0134 (0.0431)	0.0147 (0.0149)
Ln(Age)	0.0182*** (0.00354)	0.0217*** (0.00624)	0.00381* (0.00216)
GVC*Ln(Age)	0.0601*** (0.00801)	0.0905*** (0.0141)	0.00874* (0.00489)
Observations	27,202	26,877	27,201
R-squared	0.342	0.192	0.346
Fem. Manager			
	Gov.	Env.	Social
GVC	0.127*** (0.00779)	0.259*** (0.0137)	0.0452*** (0.00475)
Fem. Manager	-0.000165 (0.00856)	-0.0258* (0.0151)	0.0312*** (0.00521)
GVC*Fem. Manager	-0.0739*** (0.0188)	-0.0599* (0.0331)	-0.0354*** (0.0115)
Observations	27,202	26,877	27,201
R-squared	0.341	0.191	0.346
Public			
	Gov.	Env.	Social
GVC	0.119*** (0.00738)	0.247*** (0.0130)	0.0388*** (0.00450)
Public	0.417*** (0.0304)	0.253*** (0.0532)	-0.0949*** (0.0185)
GVC*Public	-0.100* (0.0544)	0.219** (0.0953)	0.0864*** (0.0332)
Observations	27,202	26,877	27,201
R-squared	0.341	0.191	0.346

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

All regressions include the controls, an intercept, country, year and sector fixed effects.

Table A4: Interactions by ESG Dimension II

	Size		
	Gov.	Env.	Social
GVC	0.111 (0.0701)	-0.0646 (0.123)	0.0401 (0.0427)
Small	0.160*** (0.0215)	0.118*** (0.0379)	0.0528*** (0.0131)
Medium	0.373*** (0.0218)	0.290*** (0.0384)	0.201*** (0.0133)
Large	0.599*** (0.0227)	0.504*** (0.0400)	0.530*** (0.0139)
GVC*Small	-0.0484 (0.0712)	0.181 (0.125)	0.00540 (0.0434)
GVC*Medium	0.00486 (0.0709)	0.284** (0.124)	0.0196 (0.0432)
GVC*Large	0.0604 (0.0712)	0.498*** (0.125)	-0.0312 (0.0434)
Observations	27,202	26,877	27,201
R-squared	0.342	0.194	0.346

	Sectors		
	Gov.	Env.	Social
GVC	0.0861*** (0.0126)	0.144*** (0.0223)	0.0343*** (0.00771)
GVC*Manuf.	0.0453*** (0.0150)	0.156*** (0.0264)	0.00796 (0.00914)
Observations	27,202	26,877	27,201
R-squared	0.341	0.192	0.345

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

All regressions include the controls, an intercept, country, year and sector fixed effects.

Table A5: Interactions by ESG Dimension III

	Region		
	Gov.	Env.	Social
GVC	0.137*** (0.0175)	0.314*** (0.0307)	0.0215** (0.0107)
GVC*EU	0.0317 (0.0201)	-0.00216 (0.0355)	0.0252** (0.0123)
GVC*Eastern Europe	-0.109*** (0.0226)	-0.128*** (0.0398)	0.00988 (0.0138)
GVC*MENA	-0.0577** (0.0239)	-0.195*** (0.0420)	0.0304** (0.0146)
Observations	27,202	26,877	27,201
R-squared	0.343	0.192	0.346
	Income		
	Gov.	Env.	Social
GVC	0.0851*** (0.00906)	0.238*** (0.0159)	0.0371*** (0.00552)
GVC*High income	0.0842*** (0.0141)	0.0316 (0.0248)	0.00816 (0.00858)
Observations	27,202	26,877	27,201
R-squared	0.342	0.191	0.346

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

All regressions include the controls, an intercept, country, year and sector fixed effects.

Table A6: Mediation Analysis by ESG Dimension

	Gov.			Env.			Social		
	NIE	NDE	TE	NIE	NDE	TE	NIE	NDE	TE
RD	0.0286*** (0.00265)	0.0996*** (0.00786)	0.128*** (0.00759)	0.0928*** (0.00589)	0.186*** (0.0142)	0.279*** (0.0143)	0.0155*** (0.00184)	0.0305*** (0.00512)	0.0460*** (0.00500)
Bus. Strategy	0.0583*** (0.00326)	0.0877*** (0.00754)	0.146*** (0.00759)	0.0962*** (0.00587)	0.190*** (0.0137)	0.287*** (0.0143)	0.0191*** (0.00186)	0.0281*** (0.00494)	0.0472*** (0.00502)
Share skilled prod.	-4.93e-05 (0.000125)	0.131*** (0.00957)	0.131*** (0.00957)	-5.21e-05 (0.000185)	0.286*** (0.0184)	0.286*** (0.0183)	-3.08e-05 (8.19e-05)	0.0467*** (0.00621)	0.0467*** (0.00620)
Share non prod.	-0.000850 (0.000552)	0.130*** (0.00956)	0.129*** (0.00958)	-0.000695 (0.000604)	0.285*** (0.0183)	0.284*** (0.0183)	-0.000606 (0.000400)	0.0466*** (0.00620)	0.0460*** (0.00621)
Formal regis.	0.000401 (0.000737)	0.117*** (0.00763)	0.118*** (0.00760)	0.000815 (0.00134)	0.250*** (0.0143)	0.251*** (0.0143)	-0.000469 (0.000505)	0.0406*** (0.00502)	0.0402*** (0.00499)
Finance	0.0101*** (0.00226)	0.113*** (0.00782)	0.123*** (0.00762)	0.0315*** (0.00454)	0.234*** (0.0145)	0.266*** (0.0143)	0.00667*** (0.00156)	0.0353*** (0.00508)	0.0420*** (0.00501)

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

All regressions include the controls, an intercept, country, year and sector fixed effects.

Each row represents a regression with the mediation channel in question.

Table A7: First Stage of IV estimation

	GVC
Public	-0.0431** (0.0212)
Fem. Manager	-0.0152** (0.00634)
Ln(Age)	0.00633** (0.00268)
Small	0.0206 (0.0169)
Medium	0.125*** (0.0171)
Large	0.284*** (0.0175)
GVC inst.	0.732*** (0.0281)
Observations	26,873
R-squared	0.228
Durbin (score) chi2(1)	3.00552
p value	(p = 0.0830)
Wu-Hausman F(1,26799)	2.99758
p value	(p = 0.0834)
F stat first stage	678.486
p value	0.0000

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A8: PSM matching variables

Variable	Treated	Control	t	p>t
Public	0.017	0.018	-0.78	0.436
Fem. Manager	0.138	0.112	4.16	0.000
Ln(Age)	2.959	2.950	0.57	0.568
Small	0.232	0.232	0.07	0.947
Medium	0.386	0.400	-1.58	0.115
Large	0.374	0.359	1.71	0.086

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Figure A1: ESG indicators and female managers

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Figure A2: ESG indicators and firm ownership

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Figure A3: Overlap (common support) of propensity scores between the treated and untreated group

Note: Outcome is ESG adoption. Psgraphs for other outcomes are available upon request.

Appendix B

Table B1. Overview of the recent literature on ESG determinants

Authors	Dependent variables	Independent variables	Methodology	Key finding	Sample
Nuhu and Alam (2023)	ESG disclosure	Board size; board composition; board gender diversity; board meetings; firm size; profitability; liquidity	Multiple regression analysis	Board gender diversity, board composition and board diligence are positively related to the level of ESG disclosure, while no relationship between board size and ESG disclosure.	BRICS listed companies between 2010-2019
Gavana et al., (2024)	ESG disclosure, social disclosure, environmental disclosure, governance disclosure	Board gender diversity; Board culture diversity; Board members; gender equality; rule of law; return on assets; total assets; firm's age; board independence; chief executive officer	OLS regression with standard errors clustered, 2SLS regression	Female directors improve ESG and government disclosure. Law increases the positive effect of female director on environmental disclosure and decreases impact on governance disclosure.	European non-financial listed firms between 2014-2022
Hmouda et al., (2024)	ESG score, environmental score, social score, governance score	Firm size, geographic location, firm position, energy sources used by firm	Multiple linear regression, collinearity tests	Geographic location and firm size significantly impact ESG score, energy source influence environmental score, while firm position has no significant effect.	416 firms in electric power supply chains between 2020-2021
El Khoury et al., (2021)	ESG score, environmental score, social score, governance score	Firm size, profitability, leverage, gdp growth, urbanization, rule of law, control for corruption, disclosure index	Fixed effects, Random effects regression, Hausman test	Firm size has a positive impact on ESG score, gdp has a negative impact on environmental score, urbanization has a positive impact on ESG score	38 listed banks on MENA countries between 2011-2019
Grassa et al., (2024)	ESG rating, environmental rating, social rating, governance rating	Firm size, firm age, leverage, return on equity, board on director size, women in board director, government ownership, institutional ownership, number of block-holders	Ordered logit regression	Firm size, return on equity and leverage are positively related to ESG rating, Board size has a positive impact on social and governance rating, government ownership has a positive and significant impact on ESG rating, Institutional ownership has a positive and significant effect on governance rating	48 listed companies on Abu Dhabi Securities Exchange and Dubai Financial Market between 2019-2021
Chung et al., (2022)	Bloomberg score, ESG score, environmental score, social score	Firm size, family ownership, Blockholder ownership, state ownership, audit, profitability, Gearing	Multiple regression analysis	Blockholder ownership is negatively related to ESG score, firm size and audit and profitability have a positive impact on ESG score	Hong Kong listed firms between 2011-2019
Sun and Zhao (2024)	ESG performance	Institutional investors, voice, exit threats and collusion	Fixed effects regression and endogeneity control	A positive relationship between institutional investors and ESG performance. This	3881 companies in China between 2009-2021

positive effect is controlled via voicing and exit threats.

Table B1. Overview of the recent literature on ESG determinants (*continued*)

Authors	Dependent variables	Independent variables	Methodology	Key finding	Sample
Ogboro et al., (2024)	ESG rating	Institutional ownership, ownership concentration, firm size, firm age, profitability, debt, funding of equity	Multiple regression analysis	Firm size, firm age and institutional ownership are positively related to ESG score, while ownership concentration negatively impact ESG score	17 listed banks on Nigerian Stock Exchange between 2016-2022
Abdul Rahman and Al Sayegh (2021)	ESG score	Profitability, firm size, leverage, economic sustainability performance,	Multiple regression analysis	Economic performance, firm size, profitability and leverage are positively related to ESG score.	1244 Asian companies between 2005-2017
Nguyen et al., (2025)	ESG performance	AI, blockchain adoption, risk management, environmental uncertainty, firm size, country size, debt to equity, sector,	Maximum likelihood structural equation modeling, endogeneity and multicollinearity check	AI, blockchain and risk management are positively related to ESG performance, risk management serves as a mediating factor between AI and blockchain and ESG	1742 Asian firms between 2014-2023
Ong et al., (2025)	ESG adoption	Education and awareness, and leadership mindset	Case study	Education, awareness and leadership mindset significantly impact ESG adoption	Malaysian micro, small and medium enterprises
Wei et al., (2023)	ESG score, environmental score, social score, governance score	Anticorruption, corruption index, firm size, women directors, board members, board size, age of board members, gdp growth, efficiency, operating income, cash non-current debt	Generalized method of moments	Anticorruption has a strong impact on sustainability performance of small firms than larger firms	820 Chinese listed firms between 2012-2021
Zhou and Lok (2024)	ESG performance	Institutional ownership, board diversity, firm size, firm leverage, return to asset, managerial ownership, ownership concentration, board meeting, board independence	Fixed effects regression	Institutional ownership has a positive impact on ESG performance, and board diversity positively moderates the relationship between institutional ownership and ESG performance	Chinese A-listed firms between 2011-2022
Wasiuzzaman and AbdulWahab (2025)	ESG disclosure	Board gender diversity, firm size, profitability, leverage, accountability, board size, board independence	OLS regression with standard errors cluster, Two-stage instrumental variables regression	Gender diversity has a strong effect on ESG disclosure in countries with high level of accountability	610 firms from 37 developed and developing countries between 2009-2016
Qasem et al., (2022)	ESG score	Government-managed institutional investors, Institutional investors' ownership, Board size, Board independence,	OLS regression with robust standard error	Government-managed institutional investors are positively and significantly related to ESG score.	206 Saudi listed firms between 2010-2019

firm age, firm size, Leverage,
Dividend

Table B2. Examples of Multinational Companies with Strong ESG Ratings and Participation in GVCs in 2025

Company name	Location	Participation in GVCs	Sector	CK's final grade	MSCI ESG rating	Sustainalytics ESG risk rating
Schneider Electric SE	France	Obtain materials from global suppliers and provide energy management and automation solutions to customers	Industrials	A ⁺	AAA	Low risk
Sims Ltd	Australia	Reprocess end-of-life materials and provide them to global suppliers as secondary raw materials	Materials	A	AAA	Low risk
Vestas Wind Systems A/S	Denmark	Produce wind energy and related services to customers and obtain materials from global suppliers	Industrials	A	AAA	Low risk
Brambles Ltd	Australia	Provide logistic solutions to global suppliers and customers	Industrials	A	AAA	Low risk
SMA Solar Technology AG	Germany	Obtain materials and components from global suppliers and produce solar inverters for solar energy systems.	Information technology	A ⁻	AAA	Low risk
Orsted A/S	Denmark	obtains renewable-energy materials, e.g. steel, cables, from global suppliers and delivers large-scale offshore and onshore wind energy projects to customers worldwide	Utilities	A ⁻	AAA	Low risk
Unilever PLC	United Kingdom	Obtain materials and agricultural commodities from global suppliers and deliver consumer goods to customers	Consumer staple goods	C ⁺	AAA	Low risk
Trane Technologies PLC	Ireland	Obtain components from global suppliers and manufacture Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning and refrigeration systems to customers worldwide	Industrials	B	AAA	Low risk
Yadea Group Holdings Ltd	China	Obtain components from global suppliers and manufacture electric two-wheel vehicles to customers worldwide	Consumer discretionary	B ⁺	AAA	Low risk
Kering SA	France	Obtain materials and components from global suppliers and produce luxury fashion and accessories to customers	Consumer discretionary	B ⁻	AAA	Low risk
BorgWarner Inc	United States	Obtain materials and components from global suppliers and deliver advanced automotive equipment and drive-train technologies to customers worldwide	Consumer discretionary	C ⁺	AA	Low risk
Enphase Energy Inc	United States	Obtain materials and components from global suppliers and produce solar microinverters and battery systems to customers	Information technology	A ⁻	AA	Low risk
Signify NV	Netherlands	Obtain materials and components from global suppliers and provide smart lighting products to customers worldwide	Industrials	B ⁺	AA	Low risk
Alstom SA	France	Obtain material and components from global suppliers and construct rail transportation systems for customers	Industrials	A ⁻	AA	Low risk
Stantec Inc	Canada	Obtain services from global suppliers and provide engineering and environmental consulting solutions to customers	Industrials	A ⁻	AA	Low risk

Source: Authors, based on company reports and the Corporate Knights database (2025).

Note: CK's final grade refers to the Corporate Knights final grade, which is a score that reflects a company's ESG performance (for more details, see the Corporate Knights Global 100 database). A⁺ indicates awarded and the top-ranked company. A indicates a score above 75%. A⁻ indicates a score between 70% and 75%. B⁺ indicates a score between 65% and 70%. B

indicates a score between 60% and 65%. B⁻ indicates a score between 55% and 60%. C⁺ indicates a score between 50% and 55%. AAA refers to Leader: firms show exceptional ESG performance. AA refers to Leader: firms show very strong ESG performance.